

A Generative System for the Design of High-Performing Shading Devices: Exploring the Daylight Potential of Weaving Patterns

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ABSTRACT: Designing and optimizing a Façade Shading Device (FSD) involves conflicting goals related to view access, visual comfort, energy, daylighting, and thermal performance. The optimization becomes particularly challenging when the FSD entails a complex geometry facing different orientations and solar exposure levels. Current literature focuses on the optimization of simple discrete FSDs based on horizontal or vertical shades, favoring one or the other depending on orientation. The optimization of complex FSDs that suit different orientations and solar angles is generally limited to the control of glass fritting or screen perforation density. Considering this, we present a novel Generative Design System to study the potential of weaving horizontal and vertical shades in the design of high-performing, three-dimensional, complex FSDs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Designing and optimizing a Façade Shading Device (FSD) is a difficult task that involves conflicting goals regarding view access, visual comfort, energy, daylighting, and building thermal performance. This task becomes particularly challenging when creating geometrically complex FSD that simultaneously face different orientations and solar exposure levels.

Current literature on discrete FSDs optimization focuses on horizontal and vertical shades, favoring one system over another, depending on orientation [1-2]. Regarding continuous FSDs, the research generally focuses on the use of fritting or perforation density to control sunlight [3]. Considering this, we present a novel Generative Design System (GDS) addressing weaving patterns for the design and optimization of three-dimensional complex FSDs that can balance conflicting daylighting design goals.

2. BACKGROUND

The standard IES LM-83 [4] focuses on Climate-based Daylight Modeling by proposing two metrics for the assessment of daylighting in buildings. The first one is the Spatial Daylight Autonomy (sDA), which measures the amount of area that reports an illuminance (E) ≥ 300 lux for at least 50% of the occupied annual schedule, i.e., that registers a Daylight Autonomy (DA) 300 lux (DA_{300lux}) $\geq 50\%$ – $sDA_{300/50\%}$. The second one is the Annual Sun Exposure (ASE), which measures the percentage of area that, under direct visible light conditions, reports at least 250 hours above 1000 lux - $ASE_{1000,250h}$. Henceforth, the acronyms $sDA_{300/50\%}$, DA_{300lux} , and

$ASE_{1000,250h}$ will be simplified to sDA, DA, and ASE, respectively.

Higher values of sDA improve daylight availability and subsequently decrease artificial lighting energy consumption. A lower ASE reduces the risk of visual discomfort. Thus, it is desirable to maximize sDA and minimize ASE. Based on the recommendations presented in [4] and assuming that $ASE_{1000,250h}$ is below 10%, or between 10% and 20% with additional strategies to mitigate glare, LEED V4.1 Daylight Credit Option 1 [5] awards the points described in Table 1.

Table 1: Use of sDA in the calculation of LEED V4.1 BD+C Daylight Credit Option 1 (values in %).

sDA _{300/50%} Credit	
≥ 40	1
≥ 55	2
≥ 75	3

However, simultaneously maximizing sDA and minimizing ASE poses an ill-defined problem since lower ASE values typically entail lower sDA scores and vice-versa. The multi-objective optimization of FSD is a useful approach in solving this problem. However, the literature presents a limited amount of studies that directly address it. Most of the related work in daylight optimization either is single-objective [3] or combines one of the metrics with energy-related metrics [6] or uses a single or limited range of solvers [6]. Additionally, the optimization of FSD geometry is generally limited to simple shading elements, such as louvers, fins, or perforated screens [3,7]. The few studies of complex FSD, such as [8], typically focus on

sizing and positioning an existing FSD, not addressing the optimization of the geometry of such systems.

Considering the current limitations, there is a need to study different approaches in the design and optimization of high-performing complex FSDs.

3. RESEARCH GOALS

We propose a cross-platform GDS that combines algorithmic design, daylight simulation, and performance optimization to design high-performing FSDs. The GDS interfaces with different design tools, namely AutoCAD and Rhino, and different analysis tools, including Radiance and Daysim for daylighting simulation. Moreover, it supports several black-box optimization algorithms.

This paper explores the potential of weaving patterns as valid daylighting design strategies. The aim is to produce complex architectural screens that adapt to different design requirements, such as building form, orientation, and daylight performance. We describe how the GDS manipulates weaving patterns to control daylight in buildings, particularly to balance sDA and ASE.

4. METHODS

The research comprises two phases with the following methods: (1) Implementation, which includes the development of the proposed GDS; (2) Evaluation, which consists of using the GDS in the refinement of weaving FSDs, and testing the GDS' optimization abilities to find designs that both maximize sDA and minimize ASE. The next sections describe in detail each phase.

4.1 GDS implementation

The proposed GDS has four modules: (1) one providing the algorithmic modeling of interweaved elements; (2) another delivering daylight simulation abilities; (3) a third one providing optimization capabilities that enable the automatic search for high-performing solutions; (4) a final one enabling designers to explore, query, and visualize the optimization results interactively.

Module 1: weaving patterns

Weaving is a technique based on bending and interweaving stripe-shaped elements that yields the potential to generate diverse, intricate patterns and structures. This module delivers the ability to create complex FSD based weaving patterns.

To implement it, we extended a previously developed framework specialized in weaving façade designs [9]. The framework is formalized in terms of higher-order functions, geometric transformation rules, and matrix algebra. The framework is entirely algorithmic and generates weaving patterns composed by multiple horizontal and vertical stripe-

based elements, strategically bent to avoid intersections. The framework allows the user to select: (1) the surface shape on which the weaving pattern will be created, (2) the numbers of horizontal and vertical stripes composing the pattern, and (3) the weaving strategy to apply. The proposed extension to this framework adds functionalities to control both the stripes' rotation and width along the façade surface in order to satisfy different shading requirements. Fig. 1 shows two examples of weaving patterns produced by the GDS.

Figure 1: Two examples of weaving patterns.

Module 2: daylight simulation

Module 2 is responsible for analyzing and comparing the performance of different solutions produced by module 1 using (1) visual analysis based on High-Dynamic Range (HDR) renders and false-color images, and (2) quantitative assessments of illuminance-based metrics in horizontal sensor grids placed at work plane height (≈ 0.75 m). To conduct both analysis types, the GDS uses Radiance and DAYSIM either directly or through DIVA 4.0 due to its ability to parallelize Radiance and DAYSIM simulations and therefore reduce calculation time.

Module 3: optimization packages

Our GDS takes full advantage of optimization and machine learning libraries available for the programming languages Python and Julia, namely, the black-box optimization algorithms available in Scikit-learn, Platypus, and JuliaOpt.

In this paper, we use black-box population-based metaheuristics and model-based optimization algorithms to explore the conflicting multi-criteria problem caused by sDA and ASE. We selected three optimization approaches: two metaheuristics – the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) and the Optimized Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimizer (OMOPSO) –, and a model-based technique that uses a Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) combining the Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel with the Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm 2 (SPEA-2) solver (GPR_SPEA2).

We selected NSGA-II due to its successful use in building design and optimization [10], and OMOPSO

because it was shown as the most performant of Particle Swarm Optimizers [11], which are particularly effective in building performance optimization [12]. For the model-based optimization approach, we selected the RBF kernel because it provides good results when combined with the SPEA2 optimizer [3], a popular optimization algorithm in performance-based design.

Module 4: optimization visualizer

Our GDS supports the interactive visualization of the optimization results. The goals are to (1) explore and assess the different solutions found in the search, particularly the Pareto-front ones, (2) identify the relevant decision variables and their domain, and (3) query the results. The visualizer includes an interactive scatter plot of dominated and non-dominated solutions and automatically traces the Pareto-front. The user can select any solution in the scatter plot, and the system interactively generates the corresponding 3D model and displays relevant information regarding design variables and daylight metrics. This on-demand 3D visualization also supports the analysis of other design factors not included in the search process, particularly the solutions' visual composition/aesthetic quality. Additionally, the visualizer creates parallel-coordinates graphs that allows the user to filter solutions by interactively selecting different ranges of values for decision variables and objectives/daylight metrics. This visualization facilitates iterative explorations and more refined optimizations.

4.2 Evaluation

The GDS evaluation entailed two experiments: (1) generation, iteration, and refinement, and (2) performance optimization. Both experiments consisted in the design of a weaving FSD for a 12 x 9 x 2.7 m test cell representing a typical office space located in a hypothetical commercial tower with an east and south curtain wall. We modeled these two openings to examine how the proposed system simultaneously handles two orientations with different types of solar exposure and penetration. Fig. 2 presents an exploded axonometric of the test cell fully annotated with the optical surface properties used in both experiments. Note that the interruption of the weaving pattern in the south screen aims at creating less obstructed views to the outside.

The optimization considered two metrics: sDA and ASE. Since the goals were to maximize sDA and minimize ASE, we used the guidelines of LEED V4.1 Building Design and Construction (BD+C) Daylight Credit – Option 1 (Table 1). Our test cell, with its fully glazed south and east façades, increased the difficulty of achieving the objective since it is challenging to

diffuse the Eastern low angle sunlight in clear sky conditions through a static FSD.

In both experiments, the calculation of sDA and ASE is based on a sensor grid located at work plane height (≈ 0.75 m) with sensors evenly spaced ≈ 0.6 m in both directions. The climate data used in the annual sky matrix generation is from Phoenix, AZ – a location dominated by clear skies [13].

Figure 2: Exploded axonometric illustration of the test cell used in the evaluation of the GDS.

Finally, the weaving FSD generative algorithm has three main discrete variables: the number of horizontal stripes $X1 \in \{6, 7, \dots, 20\}$, the rotation of the south horizontal stripes $X2 \in \{-\pi, -\pi + 0.02, \dots, \pi\}$, and the reduction factor of the east horizontal stripes $X3 \in \{0, 0.02, \dots, 1.6\}$. Regarding $X2$, 0 or π values generate parallel horizontal stripes in the center of the south façade, while $\pi/2$ or $3\pi/2$ create perpendicular ones. Regarding $X3$, the range results from a sinusoidal behavior wherein 0 means no reduction, and 1.6 means maximum reduction. The following describes the two experiments.

Experiment 1: generation, iteration and refinement

This experiment focused on assessing the GDS' generative and daylight abilities in a user-driven iterative process. It illustrates how a user can incrementally refine the design of an FSD based on the feedback provided by the proposed digital tool. In this experiment, point-in-time HDR renders and false-color images complemented the assessment of sDA, DA, and ASE. The production and visualization of those point-in-time images helped the designer evaluate the spatial and lighting quality of the solutions under specific circumstances. Due to space constraints, we present two user-driven explorations to illustrate the iterative use of the tool.

Experiment 2: performance optimization

In this experiment, we tested the GDS' capability to automatically search for solutions that yield a good balance between sDA and ASE, in two phases. In the first one, we used the GDS to test the performance of

the selected optimization algorithms in advancing plausible trade-offs to the optimization problem. The analysis of the first optimization results allowed us to detect, isolate, and redefine the most sensible decision variables for a more refined optimization in the second phase. The refinement consisted of first selecting the two best performing search algorithms and, then, constraining the range of the most sensible decision variables. The restraining focused the search in areas of the solution space that yield more potential to contain high-performance candidates. In both phases, the unconstrained optimization used the following objective functions:

$$\min f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = ASE_{1000,250h}(x_1, x_2, x_3) \quad (1)$$

$$\max g(x_1, x_2, x_3) = sDA_{300/50\%}(x_1, x_2, x_3) \quad (2)$$

where x_1 , x_2 , and x_3 are the variables of the algorithm that produces the weaving FSD (see section 4.2). All optimization runs analyzed 400 solutions grouped in populations or swarms of 20.

5. RESULTS

The following presents the results per experiment.

5.1 Experiment 1 results

A designer used our GDS to explore different solutions to the problem. Based on the analysis of both ASE and sDA results, the user selected a point-of-view (POV) and a time event of interest to conduct a visualization of the proposed design with HDR renders and false-color images that mapped illuminance and luminance on the room surfaces. Fig. 3 shows the results of the initial design solution proposed by the user, which has 8 horizontal stripes (x_1), a rotation of -1.5 radians (x_2), and a reduction factor of 0.75 (x_3). The goal was to allow some view in the east façade and to channel light in the south façade by tilting the stripes towards the sky. To assess east low sun angles, the user decided to conduct a point-in-time visual analysis of a POV that overlooked the southeast corner at 9 am in Winter solstice. This initial solution reported an sDA of 74.3% and an ASE of 34.7% . The good sDA score came at the expense of admitting too much direct light.

Based on the results, the user changed the rotation of the south façade horizontal stripes (x_2) to 1.1 radians to block direct light (Fig. 4). This solution reduced ASE to the acceptable value of 15.3% , but sDA dropped to a low score of 32.3% , demonstrating the limitations of using iteration in balancing both metrics.

Figure 3: Initial solution. Top: DA and ASE distribution in grid of sensors. Bottom: Illuminance contour mapped on HDR render (left) and luminance false color image (right) of the select POV at winter solstice 9 am.

Figure 4: Alternative solution. Top: DA and ASE distribution in grid of sensors. Bottom: Illuminance contour mapped on HDR render (left) and luminance false color image (right) of the select POV at winter solstice 9 am.

5.2 Experiment 2 results

Fig. 5 compares the different search mechanisms used in the first phase of this experiment. It shows that NSGA-II outperformed OMOPSO and GPR_SPEA2, which was the least performant. Both NSGA-II and OMOPSO found solutions scoring 2 points in the LEED V4.1 Daylight Credit Option 1. NSGA-II found solutions with a better sDA score than OMOPSO.

Fig. 6 Parallel-coordinates graph maps all the solutions analyzed in terms of their decision variables, sDA, and ASE score. The figure also presents the result of an interactive filter of the solutions by acceptable ranges of sDA ($\geq 40\%$) and ASE ($\leq 20\%$).

Figure 5: NSGAI, OMOPSO, and GPR_SPEA2 optimization results and their respective Pareto-fronts.

Figure 6: Parallel-coordinates analysis of the results of the first optimization phase. The filtered solutions are color-coded by sDA and are the ones that yield acceptable values of sDA and ASE.

The Parallel-coordinate visualization showed that the variable X3 (reduction factor of the east stripes) is the least influential. Therefore, the GDS can balance higher porosity levels in the east façade by controlling the size, proportion, and rotation of the south horizontal elements. The key variables are X1 (number of horizontal stripes) and X2 (rotation of the south stripes). The most successful designs in balancing ASE and sDA limit X1 to the range [6, 9] and X2 to $[33\pi/10, 64\pi/10]$.

Based on these results, the second phase of this experiment refined the optimization process by only using NSGA-II and OMOPSO and constraining X1 and X2 to the intervals mentioned above. We still selected OMOPSO since it had just a slightly worse behavior than NSGA-II in the first phase. Fig. 7 shows that both algorithms have very similar results. OMOPSO conducted broader searches, identifying solutions that yield the highest sDA scores. NSGA-II found solutions with the best balance between the two metrics, despite the small difference to analogous solutions found by OMOPSO.

The constraining of the optimization problem resulted in a higher number of solutions that yield a good tradeoff between ASE and sDA. In the first phase, OMOPSO and NSGA-II identified a total of 20 solutions eligible to score a LEED V4.1 Daylight Credit.

In the second phase, the same algorithms found 32, with 2 solutions yielding higher sDA than the best LEED V4.1 Daylight Credit qualified solution found in the first phase.

Figure 7: Results of the second optimization experiment.

6. DISCUSSION

The first experiment showed the generative and simulation capabilities of our tool by allowing users to develop design solutions based on feedback from simulation. It also revealed that an iterative use of the GDS benefits from combining quantitative data with spatial visualizations. Fig. 3 and 4 illustrate how on-demand HDR-based visualizations properly depict spatial light distribution patterns. Designers can explore this feature to complement quantitative simulation data. The experiment also showed the limitations of a user-driven iterative approach. Although the designer used the analysis feedback to propose a design alternative, the new solution was insufficient, indicating that iterative design and analysis tasks can be time-consuming and biased to the finding of few satisfactory solutions.

The second experiment showed the tool's ability to use several optimization algorithms to explore the solution space effectively. It demonstrated the benefits of conducting a two-stage optimization workflow that first compares the effectiveness of several search algorithms and isolates key decision variables to then conduct a more refined search in the second stage. The results of the first phase showed that the metaheuristic approaches (OMOPSO and NSGA-II) were better than the model-based one (GPR_SPEA2). Nevertheless, this finding does not exclude the usefulness of model-based approaches; they rather stress that design optimization is problem-dependent and that there is no universal approach. The results of the first stage also showed the benefits of using multi-objective optimization in the design of complex FSDs over user-driven approaches. Only in the first optimization, the GDS was able to find 24 eligible solutions to score at least

1 point in the LEED V4.1 Daylight Credit (Option 1) and 3 solutions qualified to 2 points. NSGA-II found the best solution with an ASE of 17.7% and an sDA of 59%. Using the GDS, we analyzed the optimization results and redefined the optimization problem by constraining the key decision variables range. As a result, the following optimization increased the pool of qualified solutions to score a LEED V4.1 Daylight credit by 60%. Moreover, all the solutions found either below ASE 10% or between 10-20% had a higher sDA score.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a modular GDS that combines 3D modeling, daylight simulation, and optimization algorithms to design high-performance FSD based on complex weaving patterns. Its modular nature allows us to use the system iteratively or as a goal-oriented design tool. Our first experiment showed how a designer could use the tool to generate and evaluate the daylight performance of weaving FSD. The visualization of the different solutions showed that by manipulating the weaved elements, it is possible to shape the lighting environment in different ways, such as redirecting and diffusing daylight or even making parts of the weaving FSD glow, acting as passive luminaires (Fig. 3 and 4). Additionally, the ability of the GSD to use a wide range of black-box optimization algorithms demonstrates its versatility in deploying goal-oriented design approaches to the multi-objective problem based on sDA and ASE. The proposed GDS can compare different search algorithms and perform a sensitivity analysis of the design variables to further refine the optimization-driven process. The second experiment demonstrated that the use of such capabilities improves the effectiveness of goal-oriented design approaches.

Nevertheless, our GDS entails two main limitations. The first is the lack of embedded expert knowledge to assist the user in iterative design-analysis tasks. When used iteratively, the tool-user interaction relies exclusively on the user's expertise. The second relates to the time cost of evaluating the objective functions, which might hamper the application of the tool in real design situations. To overcome such limitations, future work contemplates the development of heuristics that effectively helps users find critical time events and POVs, such as those proposed in [14], and the use of faster daylight simulation techniques as the ones suggested in [15]. Future developments will also include the study of different complex FSD.

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